

A VARIANT OF THE FROBENIUS PROBLEM AND GENERALIZED SUZUKI SEMIGROUPS

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Abstract

Given relatively prime positive integers a_1, \dots, a_k , let S denote the set of all linear combinations of a_1, \dots, a_k with nonnegative integral coefficients. The Frobenius problem is to determine the largest integer $g(S)$ which is not representable as such a linear combination. A related question is to determine the set $B(S)$ of integers x that are representable as differences $x = s_1 - a_1 = \dots = s_k - a_k$ for some $s_i \in S$. The construction $B(S)$ can be iterated to obtain a chain of numerical semigroups. We compare this chain to the one obtained by iterating the Lipman semigroup construction. In particular, we consider these chains for generalized Suzuki semigroups.

1. Introduction

Let a_1, \dots, a_k be relatively prime positive integers. Then all sufficiently large integers are representable as linear combinations of a_1, \dots, a_k with nonnegative integral coefficients. The Frobenius problem is to determine the largest nonrepresentable integer. Here, we are interested in a related problem. To describe this variant, we use the language of numerical semigroups. For a general reference on numerical semigroups, see [1], [3], [4], or [5].

Throughout this paper, \mathbb{N} denotes the set of positive integers and $\mathbb{N}_0 := \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ denotes the set of nonnegative integers. A numerical semigroup is an additive submonoid of \mathbb{N}_0 whose complement in \mathbb{N}_0 is finite. Given a_1, \dots, a_k as above, the numerical semigroup generated

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by a_1, \dots, a_k is $S = \langle a_1, \dots, a_k \rangle$ where

$$\langle a_1, \dots, a_k \rangle := \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^k x_i a_i : x_i \in \mathbb{N}_0 \right\}.$$

Since there is no loss of generality in doing so, we assume that S is expressed in terms of a minimal generating set; that is,

$$a_1 < \dots < a_k \text{ and } a_i \notin \langle a_1, \dots, a_{i-1}, a_{i+1}, \dots, a_k \rangle$$

for all $1 \leq i \leq k$. In this case, the integers a_1, \dots, a_k are called the generators of S , and S is said to be k -generated. The Frobenius number of S , denoted $g(S)$, is the largest integer in $\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus S$. We refer to the book [11] where a complete account of the Frobenius problem can be found. Since this paper only concerns numerical semigroups, we often use the term semigroup for short.

In this paper, we consider two semigroups that can be constructed from a given one: the dual and the Lipman semigroup. The dual of a numerical semigroup S is given by

$$B(S) := \{x \in \mathbb{N}_0 : x + S \setminus \{0\} \subseteq S\}.$$

One can check that $B(S)$ is a numerical semigroup containing S . We notice that $g(S)$ is the largest element of $B(S) \setminus S$. The Lipman semigroup of S is defined to be

$$L(S) := \langle a_1, a_2 - a_1, a_3 - a_1, \dots, a_k - a_1 \rangle$$

where the integers a_1, \dots, a_k form a minimal generating set of S . Note that $S \subseteq L(S)$. Determining the dual of S is related to the Frobenius problem since $g(S)$ is the largest element of $B(S) \setminus S$.

The dual and Lipman constructions can be iterated as in [1] to obtain two chains of numerical semigroups:

$$\begin{aligned} B_0(S) \subseteq B_1(S) \subseteq B_2(S) \subseteq \dots \subseteq B_{\beta(S)}(S) &:= \mathbb{N}_0 \\ \text{and} \\ L_0(S) \subseteq L_1(S) \subseteq L_2(S) \subseteq \dots \subseteq L_{\lambda(S)}(S) &:= \mathbb{N}_0. \end{aligned}$$

Because $B(S) \subseteq L(S)$, it is natural to ask which semigroups S satisfy

$$B_i(S) \subseteq L_i(S) \text{ for all } i \in \mathbb{N}_0. \tag{1}$$

It was conjectured in [1] that (1) holds for all numerical semigroups S . While this was shown to be false in [2], it does hold for several large classes of numerical semigroups, including 2-generated semigroups [2], those generated by generalized arithmetic progressions [9], and 3-generated telescopic semigroups [10]. Here, we show that (1) holds for generalized Suzuki semigroups. This gives an infinite family of telescopic 4-generated semigroups for which (1) holds.

It remains an open question to characterize those S for which $B_i(S) \subseteq L_i(S)$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N}_0$; in particular, we do not know if (1) holds in the following cases: S is 3-generated; S is symmetric; and S is telescopic. The smallest known counterexample to (1) is 4-generated but is not symmetric.

2. Generalized Suzuki semigroups

Given positive integers p and n , let

$$S(p, n) = \langle a, b, c, d \rangle$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a &= p^{2n+1}, \\ b &= p^{2n+1} + p^n, \\ c &= p^{2n+1} + p^{n+1}, \text{ and} \\ d &= p^{2n+1} + p^{n+1} + 1. \end{aligned}$$

If $p = 2$, then $S(p, n)$ is the Weierstrass semigroup of the point at infinity on the curve X defined by

$$y^{p^{2n+1}} - y = x^{p^n}(x^{p^{2n+1}} - x)$$

over $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2n+1}}$ [6]. Because the automorphism group of X is a Suzuki group (see [7], [12], [13]), $S(p, n)$ is sometimes called a generalized Suzuki semigroup.

We now consider some basic properties of generalized Suzuki semigroups.

Definition 1 *Given a numerical semigroup S with generators a_1, \dots, a_k (not necessarily in increasing order), let $d_i = \gcd(a_1, \dots, a_i)$ and $S_i = \langle \frac{a_1}{d_i}, \dots, \frac{a_i}{d_i} \rangle$ for $1 \leq i \leq k$. Then S is said to be **telescopic** if and only if $\frac{a_i}{d_i} \in S_{i-1}$ for all i , $2 \leq i \leq k$.*

Proposition 2 *For all positive integers p and n , $S(p, n)$ is telescopic.*

Proof. To see that a generalized Suzuki semigroup is telescopic, we must rearrange the generators. In particular, we express $S(p, n)$ as

$$S(p, n) = \langle p^{2n+1}, p^{2n+1} + p^{n+1}, p^{2n+1} + p^n, p^{2n+1} + p^{n+1} + 1 \rangle.$$

Then

$$d_1 = p^{2n+1}, \quad d_2 = p^{n+1}, \quad d_3 = p^n, \quad \text{and} \quad d_4 = 1.$$

It follows immediately that

$$\frac{a_2}{d_2} \in \mathbb{N}_0 = \langle 1 \rangle = S_1,$$

$$\frac{a_3}{d_3} = p^{n+1} + 1 = (p - 1)p^n + (p^n + 1) \in \langle p^n, p^n + 1 \rangle = S_2, \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{a_4}{d_4} = p^{2n+1} + p^{n+1} + 1 = p^n(p^{n+1}) + (p^{n+1} + 1) \in \langle p^{n+1}, p^{n+1} + 1, p^{n+1} + p \rangle = S_3.$$

Therefore $S(p, n)$ is telescopic.

Recall that a semigroup S is symmetric if and only if there is a bijection

$$\begin{aligned} \phi : S \cap \{0, \dots, g\} &\rightarrow \mathbb{N}_0 \setminus S \\ s &\mapsto g - s \end{aligned}$$

where $g := g(S)$ denotes the Frobenius number of S .

Lemma 3 [8, Lemma 6.5] *If $S = \langle a_1, \dots, a_k \rangle$ is telescopic (where a_1, \dots, a_k may not be in increasing order), then*

1. *the Frobenius number of S is $g(S) = \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{d_{i-1}}{d_i} - 1 \right) a_i$ where $d_0 = 0$; and*
2. *S is symmetric.*

Applying Proposition 3, one can see that the Frobenius number of $S(p, n)$ is

$$g(S(p, n)) = p^{2n+1} (2p^n + p - 2) - p^{n+1} - 1.$$

3. Chains of semigroups

We begin this section with a discussion of two chains of semigroups that can be formed from a numerical semigroup S . To obtain the chain of duals, set $B_0(S) := S$ and define $B_i(S) := B(B_{i-1}(S))$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$. To obtain the chain of Lipman semigroups, set $L_0(S) := S$ and define $L_i(S) := L(L_{i-1}(S))$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Each chain is finite since $\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus S$ is finite. It is also easy to verify that $B_1(S) \subseteq L_1(S)$ since $x \in B_1(S)$ implies $x + a_1 \in S$, where a_1 is the smallest nonzero element of S . This gives

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} B_0(S) & \subseteq & B_1(S) & \subseteq & B_2(S) & \subseteq & \dots & \subseteq & B_{\beta(S)}(S) \\ & & \parallel & & \cap & & & & \parallel \\ L_0(S) & \subseteq & L_1(S) & \subseteq & L_2(S) & \subseteq & \dots & \subseteq & L_{\lambda(S)}(S) \end{array}$$

for any numerical semigroup S . In this section we will show that $B_i(S(p, n)) \subseteq L_i(S(p, n))$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N}_0$. To do this, we first determine the chain of Lipman semigroups.

Lemma 4 *If $S = S(p, n)$, then*

$$L_i(S) = \langle p^n, p^n(p - i + 1) + 1 \rangle$$

for $1 \leq i \leq p$, and

$$L_{p+1}(S) = \mathbb{N}_0.$$

Proof. By definition, $L_1(S) = \langle p^{2n+1}, p^n, p^{n+1}, p^{n+1} + 1 \rangle = \langle p^n, p^{n+1} + 1 \rangle$. Viewing $L_1(S)$ as $L_1(S) = \langle p^n, p^n(p - 1 + 1) + 1 \rangle$, it is easy to see that $L_i(S) = \langle p^n, p^n(p - i + 1) + 1 \rangle$ for $1 \leq i \leq p$. Taking $i = p + 1$ gives $L_{p+1} = \langle p^n, 1 \rangle = \mathbb{N}$.

In light of Lemma 4, to prove that $B_i(S(p, n)) \subseteq L_i(S(p, n))$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N}_0$, it suffices to show that $B_i(S(p, n)) \subseteq L_i(S(p, n))$ for $2 \leq i \leq p$. The following result describes $B_i(S(p, n))$ for i in this range.

Lemma 5 *If $S = S(p, n)$ and $g = g(S)$, then*

$$B_{i+1}(S) \setminus B_i(S) = \left\{ g - \sum_{j=1}^i \alpha_j : \alpha_j \in \{a, b, c, d\} \right\}$$

for all $i, 0 \leq i < p$.

Proof. Set $B_i := B_i(S)$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N}_0$. It is known [1, Lemma I.1.8] that if a semigroup T is symmetric then $B(T) = T \cup \{g(T)\}$. So, since $S = B_0$ is telescopic (by Proposition 2) then B_0 is symmetric (by Lemma 3) and therefore $B_1(B_0) = B_0 \cup \{g(B_0)\}$. Thus, $B_1 \setminus S = \{g\}$, and the result holds for $i = 1$. We now proceed by induction on i .

Assume $B_i \setminus B_{i-1} = \{g - (\alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_{i-1}) : \alpha_j \in \{a, b, c, d\} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq i-1\}$. Define $C := \{g - (\alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_i) : \alpha_j \in \{a, b, c, d\} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq i\}$. We will show that $B_{i+1} \setminus B_i = C$.

First, we will prove that $B_{i+1} \setminus B_i \subseteq C$. Suppose $x \in B_{i+1} \setminus B_i$. This implies $x + B_i \subseteq B_i$ but $x + B_{i-1} \not\subseteq B_{i-1}$. Hence, there exists $y \in B_{i-1}$ such that $x + y \in B_i \setminus B_{i-1}$. By the induction hypothesis, $x + y = g - (\alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_{i-1})$ with $\alpha_j \in \{a, b, c, d\}$ for $1 \leq j \leq i-1$.

We claim that $y \in \{a, b, c, d\}$. We first show that y is a generator of B_{i-1} . Suppose the contrary; that is, suppose $y = s + t$ where $s, t \in B_{i-1} \setminus \{0\}$. Then $x + s + t = x + y = g - (\alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_{i-1})$ and so $x + s = g - (\alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_{i-1}) - t$. Since $x \in B_{i+1}$ and $s \in B_{i-1} \setminus \{0\} \subseteq B_i \setminus \{0\}$, we have that $x + s \in B_i$. As a consequence, $x + s + (B_{i-1} \setminus \{0\}) \subseteq B_{i-1}$. It follows that $x + s + t \in B_{i-1}$ because $t \in B_{i-1} \setminus \{0\}$. Hence, $x + y \in B_{i-1}$, which is a contradiction as $x + y \in B_i \setminus B_{i-1}$ from above. We now have that y is a generator of B_{i-1} and so

$$y \in \{a, b, c, d\} \cup \{g - (\alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_{i-2}) : \alpha_j \in \{a, b, c, d\} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq i-2\}.$$

Suppose $y = g - (\beta_1 + \dots + \beta_{i-2})$ where $\beta_j \in \{a, b, c, d\}$ for all $1 \leq j \leq i-2$. Then $x = g - (\alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_{i-1}) - g + (\beta_1 + \dots + \beta_{i-2})$ and so $x \leq (i-2)d - (i-1)a = (i-2)(d-a) - a$. Since $i \leq p$, we have that $x \leq (p-2)(d-a) - a = -p^{2n+1} + p^{n+2} - 2p^{n+1} - 2 < 0$ which is a contradiction. This proves the claim that $y \in \{a, b, c, d\}$. Therefore, we have that $x = g - (\alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_{i-1}) - y \in C$, and so $B_{i+1} \setminus B_i \subseteq C$.

Next we will show that $C \subseteq B_{i+1} \setminus B_i$. By the induction hypothesis, $C \cap B_i = \emptyset$. Hence, it suffices to show that $C \subseteq B_{i+1}$. To this end, we will show that $x + y \in B_i$ for all $x \in C$ and $y \in B_i \setminus \{0\}$. We do this by showing that the sum of the smallest elements in C and $B_i \setminus \{0\}$ is greater than $g(B_i)$. Note that the smallest element of C is $g - id$. We claim that the smallest nonzero element of B_i is a .

Suppose there exists $z \in B_i \setminus \{0\}$ such that $z < a$. By the induction hypothesis, this yields

$$a > z \geq g - (i-1)d \geq g - (p-1)d \geq p^{2n+1} + p^{2n+1}(2p^n - 2) - p^{n+2} - p \geq a,$$

and so a is the smallest nonzero element of B_i .

Now, in order to determine the Frobenius number of B_i we use [1, Proposition I.1.11(a)] stating that for any numerical semigroup T , $g(B(T)) = g(T) - \mu(T)$ where $\mu(T)$ is the multiplicity of T , that is, the least nonzero element in T . Thus,

$$g(B_i) = g - ia$$

since a is the smallest element of B_j other than 0 for all $1 \leq j \leq i$.

Suppose now that $x \in C$ and $y \in B_i \setminus \{0\}$. Then

$$x + y \geq g - id + a = g - ia - i(p^{n+1} + 1) + p^{2n+1} \geq g - ia + p^{2n+1} - p^{n+2} + p^{n+1} - p + 1 > g - ia$$

since $p^{2n+1} - p^{n+2} + p^{n+1} - p = p(p^n(p^n - p + 1) - 1) > 0$; that is, $x + y > g(B_i)$. Thus, $x \in B_{i+1}$ and so $C \subseteq B_{i+1} \setminus B_i$. Therefore,

$$B_{i+1} \setminus B_i = \left\{ g - \sum_{j=1}^i \alpha_j : \alpha_j \in \{a, b, c, d\} \right\}.$$

for all i , $0 \leq i < p$.

Theorem 6 *If $S = S(p, n)$, then*

$$B_i(S) \subseteq L_i(S)$$

for all $i \geq 0$.

Proof. Since $B_0(S) = S = L_0(S)$, $B_1(S) \subseteq L_1(S)$, and $L_{p+1}(S) = \mathbb{N}_0$, it suffices to show that

$$B_i(S) \subseteq L_i(S)$$

for all $2 \leq i \leq p$. To do this, we will prove that

$$B_p(S) \subseteq L_1(S).$$

It is known [11] that if a and b are relatively prime integers then $g(\langle a, b \rangle) = ab - a - b$. Since $L_1(S) = \langle p^n, p^{n+1} + 1 \rangle$ by Lemma 4, we then have that the Frobenius number of $L_1(S)$ is

$$g(L_1(S)) = p^{2n+1} - p^{n+1} - 1.$$

Let $x \in B_p(S) \setminus \{0\}$. By Lemma 5,

$$x \geq g - (p - 1)d \geq g(L_1(S)) + p^{2n+1}(2p^n - 2) - p^{n+2} + p^{n+1} - p + 1 > g(L_1(S)).$$

Therefore, $x \in L_1(S)$. It follows that for all $0 \leq i \leq p$,

$$B_i(S) \subseteq B_p(S) \subseteq L_1(S) \subseteq L_i(S).$$

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